

Evaluation of EMF Exposure from Distributed MIMO Antennas for 6G in an Industrial Indoor Environment

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Abstract—Distributed multi-input multi-output (D-MIMO) is one of the promising technology components for the 6G mobile communication systems. In this paper, electromagnetic field (EMF) exposure from D-MIMO deployment scenarios in an industrial indoor environment is evaluated using a hybrid simulation approach, based on ray-tracing and full-wave simulations, for downlink transmission at 3.5 GHz. For comparison, EMF exposure from a massive MIMO (mMIMO) deployment scenario is also assessed in the same environment. Both single-user equal gain transmission (EGT) precoding and multi-user centralized zero-forcing (CZF) precoding schemes are considered. EMF exposure is assessed with the metrics of incident power density, local specific absorption rate (SAR), and whole-body average SAR. The dependence of the exposure on the number of simultaneously served users and number of distributed radio units is investigated. The simulated exposure at the ground level is well below the limits specified in the international EMF exposure guidelines considering realistic output power levels for both D-MIMO and mMIMO scenarios. It is observed that the 95th and 99th percentiles of the assessed EMF exposure levels from D-MIMO are lower than those from the mMIMO deployment under the same condition. However, a trend is not observed for the median exposure levels.

Index Terms—5G, 6G, distributed MIMO, EMF exposure, hybrid simulation, incident power density, massive MIMO, specific absorption ratio (SAR).

I. INTRODUCTION

MOBILE communication technologies have been greatly revolutionized over the past decades. The traffic growth over the different generations of mobile communication systems has been managed by a combination of larger bandwidths, refined radio interfaces, and network densification [1]. One of the key technologies used by 5G base stations (BSs) to provide higher data rates is the employment of massive multiple-input multiple-output (mMIMO) array antennas consisting of a large number of antenna elements [2]. The overall network performance using cell densification with traditional antennas, including mMIMO antennas, however, does not scale with the number of BSs without proper coordination between them due to inter-cell interference [3].

A potential solution to break the interference limitation and achieve higher network capacity is to use distributed

antenna deployments [1], [3]–[7]. Distributed MIMO (D-MIMO), which is also referred to as cell-free MIMO in the literature, can be thought of as a combination of ultra-dense networks and coordinated multi-point transmission, and it is regarded as a potential candidate for beyond 5G and 6G systems [3], [5], [6]. In current deployments, where user equipment (UE) is served mainly by one centralized BS, technologies like carrier aggregation and dual connection enable the network to use a few BSs to simultaneously serve the same UE. In D-MIMO, the user equipments (UEs) can be served by many more distributed radio units (DRUs) with improved interference management, and each DRU with much lower output power than that of a centralized BS. In such a network, the DRUs are spread and connected through fronthaul links to one or more central processing units (CPUs) [3]. D-MIMO can bring improved overall network performance, such as providing higher average data rates and spectrum efficiency, seamless coverage, and increased connection density [1], [3], [4], [6], [7]. The D-MIMO technology is one of the key study items in the EU flagship 6G projects Hexa-X [8] and Hexa-X-II [9]. Radio architecture and models, signal processing techniques, resource allocation, etc., have been identified as working items for D-MIMO in 6G.

When a new generation of mobile technology is introduced, questions about EMF exposure and the safety of this technology may be raised. The EMF exposure limits applicable for radio equipment are given in terms of basic restrictions (physical quantities inside the body) and reference levels (external field quantities derived from the basic restrictions) according to the international EMF exposure guidelines provided by the International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) [10]. The reference levels are provided for the purpose of more practical means of demonstrating compliance with the guidelines. At the frequency of 3.5 GHz, being of interest in this paper, the basic restrictions are defined by the metric specific absorption rate (SAR), while the reference levels are defined by the incident power density. Basic restrictions and reference levels are specified for whole-body and local exposure [10].

The World Health Organization (WHO) and many national health agencies have concluded that the scientific evidence has not linked EMF exposure from mobile technologies, including 5G, with any impact on health at levels below the ICNIRP guidelines [11], [12]. To provide public information and address questions regarding EMF exposure, health agencies, academia, network operators, and equipment manufacturers

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have undertaken extensive measurement surveys on commercial networks to determine the environmental EMF levels, which are typically well below the limits in the international exposure guidelines. Measurement results regarding EMF exposure from 2G, 3G, and 4G BSs in various environmental categories can be found, for example, in [13]–[19]. In-situ measurement surveys of the EMF exposure from BSs have also been conducted for 5G networks in the frequency range 1 (FR1; from 0.41 to 7.125 GHz) in [19]–[24] and in FR2 (from 24.25 to 71.0 GHz) [20], [25]. Simulation results for 5G deployments have been presented in [26]–[30]. All these works have reported that the evaluated EMF levels from all technologies are at a small fraction of the EMF exposure limits. Based on the published data for the earlier generations of mobile communications, it can be expected that the typical environmental EMF exposure from 6G networks will also be well below the limits.

For each generation of mobile technologies, the methods used to assess the maximum EMF exposure from BSs have evolved to consider the characteristics of the radio transmission. For example, extrapolation from reference signal measurements and field combining from MIMO technologies are relevant when assessing the EMF exposure from a particular type of equipment or technology [31]. Since, at this moment, there is no 6G network available for measurements, the best effort is to investigate the EMF exposure from D-MIMO numerically. For example, in [32], a simple approach for the purpose of compliance assessment, based on numerical studies, has been proposed for 6G D-MIMO deployment to account for the contribution from adjacent DRUs.

In contrast to in-situ measurements, numerical simulations can provide information for both reference levels and basic restrictions. A full-wave simulation, including the antennas and the surrounding electrically large environment, to evaluate the EMF exposure is infeasible due to the large computational demand. A solution is to use hybrid simulation approaches, with which the antennas and human phantoms exposure are simulated by full-wave methods, while the field propagation is simulated by asymptotic approaches, such as ray-tracing methods. The hybridization of full-wave and ray-tracing methods has been introduced for indoor propagation studies in [33] and for the assessment of human exposure from a conventional single-antenna BS in an urban microcell in [34].

By using a hybrid approach, pioneering studies assessing the downlink (DL) EMF exposure for 6G D-MIMO deployment and comparing it to the exposure for 5G mMIMO deployment have been presented in [28], [29]. However, considering the early stage of 6G D-MIMO research, more studies are needed to look at various aspects that impact EMF exposure. In this paper, the EMF exposure from 6G D-MIMO deployment scenarios is assessed and compared with that from a 5G mMIMO deployment scenario at 3.5 GHz. The EMF exposure is assessed for both equal-gain transmission (EGT) precoding and centralized zero-forcing (CZF) precoding schemes [30], [35]–[37]. The study is performed using a realistic factory model, and mMIMO and D-MIMO DRUs equipped with representative array antenna designs. The DL environmental EMF exposure in terms of incident power density is evaluated

Fig. 1: Battery factory model used for the study: (a) top, (b) side, and (c) perspective view. The ceiling and the wall in the front are hidden in the figures for visualization purpose.

at several different heights throughout the entire factory. In addition to incident power density, local- and whole-body exposure are evaluated by means of SAR using homogeneous whole-body phantom. The effects of the number of DRUs, UE positions, number of simultaneously served UEs, and different power normalization conditions on the statistical EMF exposure levels are investigated.

It should be mentioned that the initial workflow that this paper is based upon has been developed in a master's thesis [30], supervised by one of the authors. In this study, the simulation framework was further developed to be able to assess the EMF exposure of the phantom with regard to the basic restrictions. Also, compared to [30], this paper includes more extensive evaluations with, e.g., more UE positions, more multi-UE scenarios, more D-MIMO deployment cases, and different power normalization conditions, and investigates how these aspects affect the statistical EMF exposure levels.

Due to the early phase of 6G studies, there has not been any standardized EMF assessment methodology yet to address D-MIMO networks. Therefore, it is anticipated that the presented study will be of interest in future standardization of exposure assessment procedures for such deployment scenarios.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II gives the description of the factory model, antenna models, phantom model, and D-MIMO and mMIMO deployment scenarios. The simulation workflow, solvers, precoding schemes, power normalization conditions, and EMF exposure quantities are presented in Section III. The numerical results and the data analyses are provided in Section IV. Discussion and conclusions are provided in Sections V and VI, respectively.

II. MODELS

A. Study Environment

The EMF assessments of the 6G D-MIMO and 5G mMIMO technologies were performed in an industrial indoor environment using a battery factory model shown in Fig. 1, provided by CST Studio Suite. CST Studio Suite 2022 was the software used for conducting the study [38]. The interior size of the factory was $48.8 \text{ m} \times 72.7 \text{ m} \times 7 \text{ m}$. The floor, ceiling, and all machines were assigned with perfect electric conductor (PEC)

Fig. 2: Top view of the battery factory model (the ceiling is hidden) with visual representation of: (a) D-MIMO deployment scenario with 24 DRU array antennas, (b) D-MIMO deployment scenario with 6 DRU array antennas, (c) mMIMO deployment scenario with one array antenna, (d) all 20 UE locations used in the study, and (e) UEs and phantom positions for 1 out of 20 studied cases, for CZF precoding with a combination of 4 UEs. All of the symbols from these figure are reused in the rest of the paper to mark the corresponding units.

material properties. The materials of the walls and the doors were concrete and steel, respectively. The windows were left as free space, i.e., no material property was assigned to them.

The EMF exposure levels were evaluated at 3.5 GHz for three deployment scenarios, two using D-MIMO and one using mMIMO technology, as presented in Fig. 2. In Fig. 2(a), the D-MIMO deployment with 24 DRU array antennas ($N_{\text{DRU}} = 24$) is presented. The DRU array antennas were placed uniformly in a grid with 12 m separation distance between the adjacent DRUs. In Fig. 2(b), the D-MIMO deployment with 6 DRUs ($N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$) is presented with 24 m separation distance between the adjacent DRUs. The DRUs in this coarser deployment ($N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$) were a subset of the DRUs in the denser deployment ($N_{\text{DRU}} = 24$). The mMIMO array antenna was placed at a point close to the center of the factory, as shown in Fig. 2(c). The DRU array antennas and the mMIMO array antenna were placed 10 cm under the ceiling facing the floor, i.e., pointing in $-z$ -direction.

In industrial environments, UE is not limited to a handset but also includes equipment like machinery and robots that require machine-type communications. In total, 20 well-separated UE positions were selected for statistical analysis of the EMF exposure levels, as shown in Fig. 2(d). Entirely uniform UE positioning was not possible due to the presence of machines. The UEs were placed 1 m above the floor oriented along the z -axis. For different deployment scenarios, the EMF exposure, from DL transmission, was evaluated for 20 cases, assuming the DRUs/mMIMO antenna serving one UE at the time ($K = 1$, where K is the number of simultaneously served UEs) for EGT precoding (see Sec. III-C regarding the precoding schemes), and each case corresponding to one fixed UE position. For CZF precoding, as the number of possible combinations of simultaneously served UEs K is very large and the simulation time for each combination is long, 20 cases with a combination of 2 UEs ($K = 2$) and 20 cases with a combination of 4 UEs ($K = 4$) were randomly chosen. After

the selection of UE combinations, the same cases were applied to the three deployment scenarios for comparison purposes.

In all cases, there was one full-body phantom per scenario, and it was always placed around one of the served UEs. Fig. 2(e) shows an example of the phantom placement for one of the studied 4-UE CZF cases. For the corresponding EGT case, only UE1 was present. For the corresponding 2-UE CZF case, UE1 and UE2 were present. For the 1-UE EGT cases and 2-UE CZF cases, the UE1 and UE2 were always the subsets of the 4-UE CZF cases. Since there was only one served UE in each case of EGT, the phantom was placed next to it. For the 2-UE and 4-UE CZF cases, the phantom was also placed next to UE1. By keeping the phantom at the same position, the EMF exposure results for different precoding schemes and K can be compared. The phantom was always placed 1 m away from UE1. However, the exact position of the phantom with respect to UE1 was not fixed but it was selected randomly for each study case (each UE1 position) separately. The phantom was always oriented facing towards the $-y$ -direction (see the coordinate system in Fig. 2), i.e. the phantom was rotated at $\varphi = 270^\circ$ around z -axis.

A full-body phantom named ‘‘Tom’’ with 1.8 m height and 70.5 kg weight from the CST bio-simulation library was used in the study, and it is shown in Fig. 3. The phantom was made of homogeneous material with the dielectric properties for the tissue-equivalent medium specified in [39]. The relative permittivity is $\epsilon_r = 37.9$, and the conductivity is $\sigma = 2.91$ S/m at 3.5 GHz.

B. Antennas

The UE was represented by a half-wavelength dipole (one feeding port) as shown in Fig. 4(a). The dipole was selected because it has omnidirectional radiation pattern, and it is commonly considered as a UE antenna in EMF exposure studies [40], [41] and in wireless communication studies below 6 GHz [27], [28], [42], [43]. For each D-MIMO DRU, $2 \times$

Fig. 3: Different views of the full-body phantom.

Fig. 4: Antenna element models for: (a) UE, and (b) DRU/mMIMO.

2 array antenna was used, while for mMIMO, 4×8 array antenna was used. The radiating element of these arrays was a dual-polarized circular patch antenna shown in Fig. 4(b). Each patch had two excitation ports for the two polarizations. The entire D-MIMO DRU and mMIMO array antennas are presented in Fig. 5. For the D-MIMO scenarios, the total number of antenna ports in the environment was $N = 8N_{\text{DRU}}$, for which $N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$ or 24 , while for the mMIMO scenario was $N = 64$.

III. METHOD

A. Simulation workflow

A hybrid simulation workflow was developed by using full-wave and ray-tracing solvers to evaluate the EMF exposure levels in an electrically large domain, such as the used battery factory environment. A flowchart of the simulation workflow is presented in Fig. 6 and it is as follows:

- 1) The workflow starts with simulating the UE and DRU/mMIMO antennas per port in free space using the full-wave solver (see Sec. III-B regarding the time-domain solver). For each antenna port, including both the UE antenna and DRU/mMIMO antenna, the antenna radiation pattern is stored as an equivalent far-field source to be used in Step 2) and Step 5).

Fig. 5: Perspective view of the array antenna models for: (a) DMIMO DRU, and (b) mMIMO.

Fig. 6: Workflow for the EMF exposure assessment for D-MIMO and mMIMO deployments by using the proposed hybrid simulation scheme. The steps are enumerated as described in Section III-A.

- 2) All equivalent far-field sources are imported from the full-wave simulations and placed in the factory model according to the DRU/mMIMO positions described in Sec. II-A. Ray-tracing simulations (see Sec. III-B regarding the asymptotic solver) are performed to derive the channel matrix from the UE antennas to the DRU/mMIMO antennas. The channel matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times K}$ is computed by evaluating the coupling coefficients between all D-MIMO DRU/mMIMO antenna ports and all active UE ports. The elements in the channel matrix obtained by the ray-tracing method are defined as [44]:

$$h_{nk} = \sum_{r=1}^{q_{nk}} A_r e^{-j2\pi f \tau_r} \quad (1)$$

where f is the frequency, q_{nk} is the number of rays between the n^{th} DRU/mMIMO antenna port ($n = 1, 2, \dots, N$) and the k^{th} UE antenna port ($k = 1, 2, \dots, K$), τ_r is the time-of-flight of the r^{th} ray, and A_r is the amplitude of the induced voltage in the n^{th} DRU/mMIMO antenna port by the r^{th} ray.

- 3) Using the obtained channel matrix \mathbf{H} from the ray-tracing simulation, the complex precoding matrix $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times K}$ employed by mMIMO or DRU array antennas for the DL transmission is calculated by using the chosen precoding scheme. $\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{w}_1, \mathbf{w}_2, \dots, \mathbf{w}_K]$, where $\mathbf{w}_1, \mathbf{w}_2, \dots, \mathbf{w}_K$ is the precoding vector applied to all DRUs or mMIMO antenna ports for the transmission to the $1^{\text{st}}, 2^{\text{nd}}, \dots, K^{\text{th}}$ UE antenna.
- 4) For the k^{th} UE antenna, the precoding vector \mathbf{w}_k obtained in the previous step is applied to the equivalent far-field sources of all DRUs or mMIMO antenna ports in the time-domain solver.

- 5) By exciting the equivalent far-field sources simultaneously with the applied precoding vector \mathbf{w}_k , the electric field distribution in the environment is simulated by the ray-tracing method for the k^{th} UE antenna.
- 6) Outside the phantom, the incident fields on the surface of a rectangular cuboid are recorded in the ray-tracing simulation for the k^{th} UE antenna. These incident fields are converted according to the equivalence theory to Huygens source in the full-wave simulation.
- 7) Using the Huygens source, the field distribution in the phantom is computed in the time-domain solver, and thereafter the SAR distribution is assessed.
- 8) Steps 4) - 7) are repeated for all active UEs (if $K > 1$).
- 9) The electric field (used to calculate the incident power density) distributions and SAR from all MIMO layers, each layer corresponding to one UE antenna, are combined in an uncorrelated way, as discussed in Sec. III-E, for each case.

The used software creates an equivalent near-field Huygens source for the full-wave simulations with the phantom. In [29], a different strategy has been followed, where plane wave full-wave simulations and combining of rays (summation and weighting) have been used to model the incident fields on a phantom.

Compared to the other studies [28], [29], the phantom was included in the ray-tracing simulations. It has been shown that the placement of the phantom in both parts of the hybrid simulation is a more accurate approach than making the equivalent source without the existence of the phantom for further SAR simulations, i.e., adding it only to the time-domain solver [45]. An improved approach for evaluating the SAR in a hybrid simulation has been presented in [46] using an iterative technique via the total-field/scattered-field (TF/SF) formulation. However, the employed software does not directly support the use cases of interest at present. Nevertheless, the iterative approach makes the simulation even more time-consuming.

To obtain the EMF exposure levels for a fixed UE or a fixed combination of UEs for each D-MIMO and mMIMO deployment scenario, a number of simulations between 5 to 14 are needed depending on K , including antenna simulations, simulations for channel sounding, field distribution simulations, and SAR simulations. Given that the number of required simulations was large for all studies and that the total number of studies was 180 (20 per each of the 9 combinations: 1) for CZF: D-MIMO with 6 DRUs, D-MIMO with 24 DRUs, or mMIMO, with 2 or 4 UEs; and 2) for EGT: D-MIMO with 6 DRUs, D-MIMO with 24 DRUs, or mMIMO, with 1 UE), the simulation workflow was fully automated and controlled via a script developed in MATLAB [47] using CST-dedicated interface.

B. Simulation solvers

For the study, the time-domain solver based on the finite integration technique (FIT) was used for the full-wave simulations, and the asymptotic solver based on the shooting and bouncing rays (SBR) method was used for the ray-tracing

simulations. Both solvers are available in the CST Studio Suite.

In the time-domain solver, the largest allowed cell size was set to 30 cells per wavelength in the corresponding medium for UE antenna simulations, 20 for DRU/mMIMO antenna simulations, and 12 for SAR computation within the phantom. The smallest allowed cell size was set to 1/10 of the maximum cell.

In the asymptotic solver, ray tubes were used. The distance of the initially launched rays was 2 free space wavelengths λ_0 (17.1 cm) for each source. The number of initially launched ray tubes was a few millions, and it increased to several tens of millions after reflection. The adaptive ray sampling configured in CST was used, which increases the ray density in areas where higher accuracy is needed by subdividing the ray tubes. The maximum ray distance, i.e., the maximum edge length of a ray tube before subdivision, was $3\lambda_0$ (25.7 cm), and the minimum ray distance, i.e., the smallest edge length of a ray tube during the adaptive subdivision process, was $0.2\lambda_0$ (1.7 cm). The mesh of the computational domain consisted of triangles which for non-planar geometries were curved. The maximum allowable length of the triangle edges was $2\lambda_0$, and the maximum allowable tolerance of the surface normal of the triangles was set to 5° . The number of mesh triangles was around six million. The maximum number of reflections was set to four, and diffraction was not considered for the trade-off between accuracy and computational time (840 simulations with the asymptotic solver were performed).

C. Precoding schemes

Antenna precoding is a process in which the amplitudes and phases of the transmitting antenna elements are dynamically set by the transmit vector \mathbf{t} according to the channel state information. The transmit vector \mathbf{t} (i.e. amplitudes and phases) depends on the precoding scheme used by the BS antenna, symbols transmitted to the UEs, and power constraint factor [29]. Thus, the transmit vector $\mathbf{t} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is given by:

$$\mathbf{t} = \sqrt{\alpha} \mathbf{W} \mathbf{s} \quad (2)$$

where α is a power constraint factor, \mathbf{s} is the transmit data symbols vector, and \mathbf{W} is the precoding matrix. The EMF exposure for both D-MIMO and mMIMO technologies was evaluated for two precoding schemes:

- 1) EGT was used for single-UE cases, i.e., $K = 1$. This is a simple precoding scheme aiming at improving the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at the receiving UE antenna [30], [35]. However, since the interference is ignored, EGT is an unrealistic precoding method for deployment scenarios with multiple UEs operating simultaneously. For EGT, the magnitude of the precoding weights of each port was set the same, while the phase was conjugate of the channel matrix elements:

$$w_{nk} = w_0 e^{-j(\arg(h_{nk}))} \quad (3)$$

where w_0 is the amplitude of the weight. w_0^2 is proportional to the configured power, i.e., the generated

power before feeding to the antenna port. To maximize the radiated power, a maximum configured power was given to each port of all array antennas as discussed in Sec. III-D1.

- 2) CZF was used for multiple-UE cases, i.e., $K = 2$ and 4. CZF aims to maximize the signal-to-interference ratio (SIR) by nullifying the interference [30], [36], [37]. CZF was considered a more realistic precoding scheme compared to MRT. A potential issue of CZF is that the signal strength at the users can become weak because of the strict zero-interference constraint [30]. The precoding matrix for CZF was calculated by:

$$\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{H}^*(\mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{H}^*)^{-1} \quad (4)$$

where $(\cdot)^T$ denotes the transpose. Note that the amplitudes of the elements in the resultant \mathbf{W} in (4) are mostly reduced from w_0 in (3), leading to reduced radiated power compared to EGT, and the amplitude reduction is different among the elements as discussed in Sec. III-D1. This is known as power tapering.

D. Power normalization

In order to compare the EMF exposure for the different deployment scenarios, precoding schemes, and number of UEs, three kinds of power normalization were carried out:

- 1) *Normalization to total configured power of 1 W for all D-MIMO DRU or mMIMO antennas:* The configured power per port per layer, P_0 , was equal to the total configured power, $P_{\text{tot,config}} = 1$ W in all scenarios, divided by the number of ports N and by the number of MIMO layers (UEs) K , i.e., $P_0 = P_{\text{tot,config}}/NK$. For EGT, each port had the same power $P_{0,\text{EGT}} = P_{\text{tot,config}}/N$, and since it was assumed that the antennas had total efficiency of 1, the total radiated power $P_{\text{tot,rad}}$ was the same as $P_{\text{tot,config}}$. For CZF, due to power tapering, only one port per layer had the configured power $P_{0,\text{CZF},K} = P_{\text{tot,config}}/NK$ after scaling by the antenna total efficiency, and the rest of the ports had lower power. This resulted in radiated power per layer lower than $P_{\text{tot,config}}/K$, and therefore $P_{\text{tot,rad}}$ lower than $P_{\text{tot,config}}$. Also, the radiated power per layer was not the same because the power tapering differed among the layers. This power normalization condition is similar to what can be used in real networks, for which total radiated power is typically lower using precoding schemes similar to CZF.

- 2) *Normalization to total radiated power of 1 W for all DMIMO DRU or mMIMO antennas:* For EGT, the normalized power was the same as in 1). For CZF, the total radiated power, $P_{\text{tot,rad}} = 1$ W, was equally split among the K layers, i.e. the radiated power per layer was set to $P_{\text{tot,rad}}/K$ after power tapering while the interference nulling was kept. The purpose of this power normalization was to compare the EMF levels with the same total radiated power by excluding the effects of power tapering.

- 3) *Normalization to fixed power of 1 μ W received by each UE antenna:* The radiated power was scaled for each MIMO layer such that the desired power $P_{\text{rec}} = 1$ μ W was received by the UE antenna. As the scaling was different for each

layer, the radiated power was not the same for the different layers. In reality, the transmitted power is bounded by the total configured power when using full-buffer traffic, and the EMF exposure levels will not scale up with the number of simultaneously served UEs. It has been shown for full-buffer traffic that the EMF exposure levels are lower if more UEs are served in mMIMO system [36], [48], [49]. The purpose of this power normalization was to compare the EMF exposure assuming that different deployment scenarios have the same link budget.

E. EMF exposure evaluation

The EMF exposure for different deployment scenarios, precoding schemes, and K were evaluated using incident power density and SAR.

The equivalent plane-wave incident power density is defined as:

$$S_{\text{inc}} = \frac{1}{2\eta_0} |E_{\text{fs}}|^2 \quad (5)$$

where η_0 is the free-space wave impedance (Ω) and $|E_{\text{fs}}|$ is the magnitude of the electric field strength in free-space (V/m). S_{inc} was compared to the reference levels of 10 W/m² specified in [10], [50] applicable for general public. While such value is intended to be spatially averaged over the whole-body surface, in this paper, spatial peak power density was conservatively used in the analysis. The electric field strength was computed as described in Step 5) of Sec. III-A using the asymptotic solver on three horizontal planes at 0.17 m, 1.33 m, and 2.5 m above the floor. Areas above this height are normally not accessible and, therefore, were not considered. S_{inc} was sampled on a uniform square grid in the horizontal plane throughout the entire factory with a sampling step of $7\lambda_0$ (60 cm). The obtained S_{inc} distributions and their cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) were used to characterize the environmental EMF exposure levels for D-MIMO and mMIMO scenarios.

The SAR was evaluated in the body phantom, which was placed close to one of the served UEs. The SAR is defined as:

$$\text{SAR} = \frac{\sigma |E_{\text{hb}}|^2}{2\rho} \quad (6)$$

where σ and ρ are the electrical conductivity (S/m) and mass density (kg/m³) of human tissue; $|E_{\text{hb}}|$ is the magnitude of the electric field strength in the tissue. Local SAR was averaged over a volume of tissue in the shape of a cube with a mass of 10 g according to the ICNIRP guidelines and compared to the basic restrictions in [10], [50] applicable for the general public corresponding to a limit value of 2.0 W/kg.

The whole-body average SAR was also calculated

$$\text{WBSAR} = \frac{P_{\text{abs}}}{m_{\text{WB}}} \quad (7)$$

where P_{abs} is the power absorbed by the phantom (W), and m_{WB} is the mass of the phantom's body (kg; given in Sec. II-A). WBSAR was compared to the basic restrictions in [10],

[50] applicable for the general public corresponding to a limit value of 0.08 W/kg. (6) and (7) were computed by using the time-domain solver, as described in Step 7) of Sec. III-A.

When considering the EMF exposure from different MIMO layers the signals are uncorrelated, and the combining of the incident power density and of the SAR is therefore determined as [51]:

$$S_{\text{inc}}(r) = \sum_{k=1}^K S_{\text{inc},k}(r) \quad (8)$$

$$SAR_{10g}(r) = \sum_{k=1}^K SAR_{10g,k}(r) \quad (9)$$

$$SAR_{\text{WB}}(r) = \sum_{k=1}^K SAR_{\text{WB},k}(r) \quad (10)$$

where r is the coordinate in the environment or human body depending on the assessed metric, $S_{\text{inc},k}$ is the incident power density from the k^{th} MIMO layer, $SAR_{10g,k}$ is the 10g-SAR from the k^{th} MIMO layer, and $SAR_{\text{WB},k}$ is the WBSAR from the k^{th} MIMO layer.

IV. RESULTS

First, the distribution of S_{inc} over a horizontal cut throughout the environment is presented in Section IV-A, and the distribution of SAR_{10g} over the body phantom is given in Section IV-B, for one of the studied cases and one of the power normalization conditions. Then, the statistical results in terms of CDFs for S_{inc} , peak SAR_{10g} , and SAR_{WB} for the three power normalization conditions are given in Sections IV-C – IV-E.

A. Examples of incident power density distribution

Examples for the S_{inc} distributions using EGT ($K = 1$), CZF ($K = 2$), and CZF ($K = 4$) are presented in Fig. 7, for D-MIMO with 24 DRUs and 6 DRUs, and mMIMO deployment scenarios. These examples are for the positions of simultaneously served UEs presented in Fig. 2(e) (the difference for the cases of $K = 1$ and $K = 2$ compared to $K = 4$ is explained in Sec. II-A) out of the 20 studied UE positions and combinations. The S_{inc} distributions shown in these figures are on the plane $z = 1.33$ m. The distributions are normalized to the same $P_{\text{tot,config}}$ of 1 W.

S_{inc} for EGT in Fig. 7(a) is higher than that for CZF in Fig. 7(b) and (c). This is expected as there is power tapering for CZF, i.e. the actual radiated power is less than 1 W while for EGT is 1 W. Also, for D-MIMO deployment, S_{inc} is more uniformly spread for EGT, while S_{inc} is centered around the UEs for CZF. This can be attributed to that CZF suppresses the power from the DRUs away from the served UE in order to mitigate the interference to other UEs. S_{inc} is overall lower for the D-MIMO deployment with $N_{\text{DRU}} = 24$ compared to S_{inc} for the D-MIMO with $N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$. This can be explained by that the configured power per DRU decreases with increasing the number of DRUs. The figures show that the mMIMO scenarios result in a higher peak value of S_{inc}

compared to D-MIMO due to the higher effective isotropic radiated power (EIRP) from a single radio unit.

B. Examples of SAR distribution

Examples of the SAR_{10g} distributions using EGT ($K = 1$), CZF ($K = 2$), and CZF ($K = 4$) are presented in Fig. 8, for D-MIMO with 24 DRUs and 6 DRUs, and mMIMO deployment scenarios. The phantom in the examples is positioned in the factory as indicated in Fig. 2(e), i.e., the same example as for S_{inc} is considered. The SAR_{10g} distributions are normalized to total configured power of 1W.

The SAR is higher in the part of the phantom facing the closest antenna. For the considered example, the closest DRU is on the right side of the phantom for the D-MIMO deployment with $N_{\text{DRU}} = 24$. Due to that, the SAR is higher on this side of the phantom. For the D-MIMO deployment with $N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$, the closest DRU is behind the phantom and the SAR is higher on the back side of the phantom. For the mMIMO deployment, the phantom faces the mMIMO array antenna, leading to higher SAR on the front side. In almost all cases, the peak local SAR was found in the extremities.

C. Statistical results for power normalization to total configured power of 1 W

Fig. 9 shows the CDFs of S_{inc} from all 20 cases for each deployment scenario and precoding scheme when using normalization to $P_{\text{tot,config}} = 1$ W. The median, 95th, and 99th percentile levels are given in Table I. The field sampling points inside PEC objects, i.e., the factory machines, were excluded so that they do not impact the results. CZF leads to statistically lower S_{inc} than EGT because of the lower radiated power resulting from the power tapering. The $P_{\text{tot,rad}}$ for CZF is presented in Fig. 10(a) and it is significantly lower than 1 W. Under this power normalization condition, $P_{\text{tot,rad}}$ in the D-MIMO CZF scenarios is lower than $P_{\text{tot,rad}}$ in the mMIMO CZF scenarios. Also, $P_{\text{tot,rad}}$ in the D-MIMO CZF scenarios with $N_{\text{DRU}} = 24$ is lower than $P_{\text{tot,rad}}$ in the scenarios with $N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$. It can be seen that the difference in $P_{\text{tot,rad}}$ between 2-UE and 4-UE is relatively small.

For EGT, the mMIMO deployment has a lower median value but higher 95th and 99th percentiles than the D-MIMO deployment. This can be explained using Fig. 7(a) in which a focused region with high S_{inc} can be observed for mMIMO, while S_{inc} outside this region is significantly lower. The mMIMO array antenna has higher peak EIRP than that of a D-MIMO DRU array antenna, which mainly contributes to the 95th and 99th percentiles. In contrast, the median value is mainly determined by the spatial spread of power, which depends on the number of array antennas (if they are well distributed). In the mMIMO scenario, S_{inc} is lower outside the main lobe region, leading to a lower median level.

For CZF, it is also observed that mMIMO has significantly higher 95th and 99th percentiles for S_{inc} than D-MIMO. For example, for CZF with $K = 4$, the 99th percentile for D-MIMO with $N_{\text{DRU}} = 24$ is 0.22 mW/m², which is only about 14% of that for the mMIMO scenario of 1.59 mW/m². In contrast, for EGT ($K = 1$), the 99th percentile for D-MIMO with $N_{\text{DRU}} =$

Fig. 7: S_{inc} distribution on the plane $z = 1.33$ m for the scenario presented in Fig. 2(e) and for power normalization to $P_{\text{tot,config}} = 1$ W: (a) EGT precoding, (b) CZF precoding with $K = 2$, and (c) CZF precoding with $K = 4$. On the left-hand side the results for the D-MIMO deployment with 24 DRUs are presented, in the middle the results for the D-MIMO deployment with 6 DRUs, and on the right-hand side the results for the mMIMO deployment.

24 is 2.69 mW/m^2 , which is about 32% of that for the mMIMO scenario of 8.49 mW/m^2 . The lower 95th and 99th percentiles ratios between D-MIMO and mMIMO for CZF compared to EGT are because CZF introduces power tapering for DRUs which is especially high for DRUs far away from active UEs. In contrast to the EGT case, for CZF the median value for S_{inc} is slightly higher for mMIMO deployment compared to D-MIMO deployment because of the higher $P_{\text{tot,rad}}$.

The data show that for CZF the D-MIMO deployment scenario with more DRUs ($N_{\text{DRU}} = 24$) has lower 95th and

99th percentile of the S_{inc} levels compared to the one with fewer DRUs ($N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$) since $P_{\text{tot,config}}$ is spread over more DRUs. This is in line with the EGT case. For CZF, however, the median value for S_{inc} levels for the D-MIMO deployment scenario with 24 DRUs is lower than the median value for the D-MIMO with 6 DRUs due to the lower $P_{\text{tot,rad}}$.

Regardless of the deployment scenario, when comparing the results for $K = 2$ with $K = 4$, slightly higher median value and slightly lower 95th for S_{inc} are found when more UEs are used. The 99th percentile for S_{inc} is lower when more UEs are

Fig. 8: SAR_{10g} distribution over the full-body phantom for the scenario presented in Fig. 2(e) and for power normalization to $P_{tot,config} = 1$ W: (a) EGT precoding, (b) CZF precoding with $K = 2$, and (c) CZF precoding with $K = 4$. On the left-hand side the results for the D-MIMO deployment with 24 DRUs are presented, in the middle the results for the D-MIMO deployment with 6 DRUs, and on the right-hand side the results for the mMIMO deployment. The views of the phantom are the same as those in Fig. 3, i.e. from the right to the left - front, left, back, and right view.

Fig. 9: CDFs for S_{inc} from all 20 study cases for the three deployments and for power normalization to $P_{tot,config} = 1$ W: (a) EGT precoding, and (b) CZF precoding.

TABLE I: S_{inc} value at different percentile levels for the three deployments, EGT and CZF precoding, and power normalization to $P_{tot,config} = 1$ W.

Precoding scheme and number of UEs	Percentile	S_{inc} (mW/m ²)		
		Deployment		
		D-MIMO $N_{DRU} = 24$	D-MIMO $N_{DRU} = 6$	mMIMO
EGT $K = 1$	median	0.47	0.41	0.16
	95 th	1.71	1.97	2.59
	99 th	2.69	3.60	8.49
CZF $K = 2$	median	0.03	0.04	0.05
	95 th	0.16	0.30	0.66
	99 th	0.31	0.66	1.89
CZF $K = 4$	median	0.03	0.05	0.07
	95 th	0.13	0.26	0.64
	99 th	0.22	0.50	1.59

activated. The trend of higher median value, but lower 95th and 99th percentile for the S_{inc} levels, when more UEs are activated, is attributed to the fact that the power is spatially spread towards more different UE locations, but the power per DRU per layer is lower.

The CDFs for peak SAR_{10g} and SAR_{WB} are presented in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, respectively. The median and 95th percentile levels are given in Table II. It can be observed that EGT leads to statistically higher SAR than CZF, as $P_{tot,rad}$ for EGT is higher for this power normalization condition. The 95th percentiles of peak SAR_{10g} and SAR_{WB} for mMIMO scenario are higher than those for the D-MIMO scenarios. Lower median and 95th percentile levels of the EMF exposure are obtained for more simultaneously served UEs.

Fig. 10: CDFs for $P_{\text{tot,rad}}$ from all 20 study cases for the three deployments: (a) CZF precoding with $K = 2$ and $K = 4$ for power normalization to $P_{\text{tot,config}} = 1$ W, and (b) CZF precoding with $K = 4$ for normalization to $P_{\text{rec}} = 1 \mu\text{W}$ by each UE.

Fig. 11: CDFs for the peak SAR_{10g} from all 20 study cases for the three deployments and for power normalization to $P_{\text{tot,config}} = 1$ W: (a) EGT precoding, and (b) CZF precoding.

Fig. 12: CDFs for SAR_{WB} from all 20 study cases for the three deployments and for power normalization to $P_{\text{tot,config}} = 1$ W: (a) EGT precoding, and (b) CZF precoding.

TABLE II: Peak SAR_{10g} and SAR_{WB} values at median and 95th percentile levels for the three deployments, EGT and CZF precoding, and power normalization to $P_{\text{tot,config}} = 1$ W.

Precoding scheme and number of UEs	Percentile	Peak SAR_{10g} (mW/kg)		
		Deployment		
		D-MIMO $N_{\text{DRU}} = 24$	D-MIMO $N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$	mMIMO
EGT $K = 1$	median	0.19	0.19	0.25
	95 th	0.23	0.52	7.58
CZF $K = 2$	median	0.02	0.05	0.04
	95 th	0.04	0.14	1.30
CZF $K = 4$	median	0.01	0.02	0.02
	95 th	0.02	0.08	0.64
		SAR_{WB} (mW/kg)		
EGT $K = 1$	median	0.0057	0.0049	0.0044
	95 th	0.0075	0.0149	0.2792
CZF $K = 2$	median	0.0007	0.0010	0.0006
	95 th	0.0013	0.0042	0.0414
CZF $K = 4$	median	0.0005	0.0006	0.0004
	95 th	0.0006	0.0022	0.0203

D. Statistical results for power normalization to total radiated power of 1 W

Fig. 13 shows the CDFs for S_{inc} from all 20 cases for each deployment scenario for CZF when using normalization to $P_{\text{tot,rad}} = 1$ W. This power is equally split among the MIMO layers. For EGT, the results are the same as those shown in Fig. 9(a). The median, 95th, and 99th percentile levels are given in Table III, and the EGT results are copied from Table I for comparison. For CZF, $P_{\text{tot,rad}}$ is larger for this power normalization than $P_{\text{tot,rad}}$ for normalization to total configured power, and so are the EMF exposure levels.

The median and 95th percentile for S_{inc} become comparable

Fig. 13: CDFs for S_{inc} from all studied cases for the three deployments, CZF precoding, and power normalization to $P_{\text{tot,rad}} = 1$ W.

TABLE III: S_{inc} value at different percentile levels for the three deployments, EGT and CZF precoding, and power normalization to $P_{\text{tot,rad}} = 1$ W.

Precoding scheme and number of UEs	Percentile	S_{inc} (mW/m ²)		
		Deployment		
		D-MIMO $N_{\text{DRU}} = 24$	D-MIMO $N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$	mMIMO
EGT $K = 1$	median	0.47	0.41	0.16
	95 th	1.71	1.97	2.59
	99 th	2.69	3.60	8.49
CZF $K = 2$	median	0.40	0.34	0.21
	95 th	2.02	2.18	2.67
	99 th	3.91	5.21	7.64
CZF $K = 4$	median	0.47	0.40	0.28
	95 th	1.73	1.96	2.58
	99 th	2.91	4.00	6.44

for EGT and CZF using power normalization to the same $P_{\text{tot,rad}}$, as shown in Table III. For mMIMO, the difference in the 99th percentile for S_{inc} between applying EGT and CZF becomes smaller, but for EGT is still higher. D-MIMO CZF has a higher 99th percentile than EGT. The reason is that the total radiated power is scaled up for CZF, and the DRUs close to the active UEs can have higher power when using this precoding scheme. The fields around these DRUs contribute to a higher 99th percentile level.

The 95th and 99th percentiles for S_{inc} for the mMIMO deployment are larger than for the D-MIMO, while the median value is lower as shown in Table III. Comparing D-MIMO with $N_{\text{DRU}} = 24$ and $N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$, the median levels are higher, but the 95th and 99th percentiles are lower for the case with more DRUs. When applying CZF, the 4-UE cases have higher median levels and lower 95th and 99th percentiles than the 2-UE cases.

The CDFs for peak SAR_{10g} and SAR_{WB} for CZF are shown in Fig. 14, while the CDFs for EGT are given in Fig. 11(a) and Fig. 12(a), respectively. The median and 95th percentile levels are given in Table IV. The SAR values experience similar to S_{inc} trend when comparing K , N_{DRU} , and different precoding schemes.

E. Statistical results for power normalization to fixed received power of 1 μW by UE

As mentioned in Sec. III-D, comparing results with different K is not relevant when using normalization to a fixed received power ($P_{\text{rec}} = 1$ μW by each UE in this case), so in this part,

Fig. 14: CDFs for (a) peak SAR_{10g} and (b) SAR_{WB} from all 20 study cases for the three deployments, CZF precoding, and power normalization to $P_{\text{tot,rad}} = 1$ W.

TABLE IV: Peak SAR_{10g} and SAR_{WB} values at median and 95th percentile levels for the three deployments, EGT and CZF precoding, and power normalization to $P_{\text{tot,rad}} = 1$ W.

Precoding scheme and number of UEs	Percentile	Peak SAR_{10g} (mW/kg)		
		Deployment		
		D-MIMO $N_{\text{DRU}} = 24$	D-MIMO $N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$	mMIMO
EGT $K = 1$	median	0.19	0.19	0.25
	95 th	0.23	0.52	7.58
CZF $K = 2$	median	0.32	0.30	0.15
	95 th	0.73	1.42	4.83
CZF $K = 4$	median	0.19	0.16	0.10
	95 th	0.38	0.71	2.60
SAR_{WB} (mW/kg)				
EGT $K = 1$	median	0.0057	0.0049	0.0044
	95 th	0.0075	0.0149	0.2792
CZF $K = 2$	median	0.0114	0.0067	0.0032
	95 th	0.0237	0.0407	0.1544
CZF $K = 4$	median	0.0064	0.0049	0.0017
	95 th	0.0122	0.0205	0.0823

only the results for $K = 4$ are presented. Fig. 10(b) shows that the mMIMO deployment has the highest total radiated power levels for this power normalization. Also, the D-MIMO deployment with more DRUs ($N_{\text{DRU}} = 24$) has lower total radiated power levels compared to the D-MIMO deployment with less DRUs ($N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$).

The CDFs of S_{inc} from all 20 cases for each deployment scenario are shown in Fig. 15. The radiated power is different among the layers for this power normalization. The median, 95th, and 99th percentile of S_{inc} are given in Table V. As one can see, the mMIMO deployment has higher 95th and 99th percentiles than D-MIMO. Regarding the median value, the results for mMIMO deployment are similar to those for

Fig. 15: CDFs for S_{inc} from all 20 study cases for the three deployments, CZF-precoding with $K = 4$, and power normalization to $P_{\text{rec}} = 1 \mu\text{W}$ by each UE.

D-MIMO with $N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$. The exposure is statistically lower for D-MIMO with $N_{\text{DRU}} = 24$ compared to $N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$.

TABLE V: S_{inc} value at different percentile levels for the three deployments, CZF precoding with $K = 4$, and power normalization to $P_{\text{rec}} = 1 \mu\text{W}$ by each UE.

Percentile	S_{inc} (mW/m ²)		
	Deployment		
	D-MIMO $N_{\text{DRU}} = 24$	D-MIMO $N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$	mMIMO
median	0.04	0.20	0.20
95 th	0.16	1.04	1.95
99 th	0.27	2.04	5.00

The CDFs for peak SAR_{10g} and SAR_{WB} for CZF with $K = 4$ are presented in Fig. 16. The median and 95th percentile levels for peak SAR_{10g} and SAR_{WB} values are given in Table VI. The SAR results show a trend similar to the results for S_{inc} . The only exception is that mMIMO has a lower median value for SAR_{WB} compared to D-MIMO with $N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$.

TABLE VI: Peak SAR_{10g} and SAR_{WB} values at median and 95th percentile levels for the three deployments, CZF-precoding with $K = 4$, and power normalization to $P_{\text{rec}} = 1 \mu\text{W}$ by each UE.

Percentile	Peak SAR_{10g} (mW/kg)		
	Deployment		
	D-MIMO $N_{\text{DRU}} = 24$	D-MIMO $N_{\text{DRU}} = 6$	mMIMO
median	0.02	0.07	0.08
95 th	0.04	0.17	0.40
SAR_{WB} (mW/kg)			
median	0.0006	0.0024	0.0016
95 th	0.0012	0.0050	0.0115

V. DISCUSSION

In all presented statistical results, the 99th percentiles of S_{inc} in the simulation region are found to be at most 5.2 mW/m² and 8.5 mW/m² (see Table III) for $P_{\text{tot,rad}} = 1$ W for D-MIMO and mMIMO, respectively. Even scaling $P_{\text{tot,rad}}$ to 10 W, which may be considered possible for indoor deployment, the corresponding 99th percentiles of S_{inc} are below 0.6% and 0.9% of the ICNIRP (whole-body) limits for general public, respectively. For D-MIMO, the 95th percentiles for SAR are found to be at most 1.4 mW/kg and 0.04 mW/kg for SAR_{10g} and SAR_{WB} (see Table IV), respectively. When

(a) peak SAR_{10g}

(b) SAR_{WB}

Fig. 16: CDFs for (a) peak SAR_{10g} , and (b) SAR_{WB} from all 20 study cases for the three deployments, CZF precoding with $K = 4$, and power normalization to $P_{\text{rec}} = 1 \mu\text{W}$ by each UE.

scaling to $P_{\text{tot,rad}} = 10$ W, the 95th percentiles are below 0.8% and 0.6% of the respective limits for general public. For mMIMO, the 95th percentile for SAR is found to be at most 7.6 mW/kg and 0.28 mW/kg for SAR_{10g} and SAR_{WB} , respectively. If $P_{\text{tot,rad}} = 10$ W, then the 95th percentile corresponds to 3.8% and 3.5% of the respective limits for general public. Thus, under the same power normalization condition, the 95th and 99th percentiles of exposure from D-MIMO are lower than those from mMIMO, and for both technologies well below the respective limits for general public. Lower 95th percentiles of EMF exposure from D-MIMO than mMIMO deployments are also observed in [28], [29]. It should be noted that the statistical results, presented in this paper, only consider 20 cases with fixed UE positions per scenario. When considering the dynamic change of the field distributions due to moving UEs and considering the bursty traffic rather than full-buffer transmission, the time-averaged EMF exposure levels are expected to be even lower.

In this paper, up to 4 reflections of the rays were considered. Increasing the number of reflections provides more accurate field results. A sensitivity analysis on the impact of the number of reflections on S_{inc} for EGT precoding has been performed in [30]. It has been observed there that S_{inc} levels increased up to 5.3 dB at the median level when the number of reflections increased from 2 to 4 in the same environment as the one used in this paper. When the number of reflections increased, the median level of statistical S_{inc} levels had larger increase compared to the increases in the 95th and 99th percentiles. All presented analyzes in this paper were based on comparative studies between mMIMO and D-MIMO deployments, and between CZF and EGT, in the same environment, power nor-

TABLE VII: Comparison between the presented work and other works available in the literature studying DL EMF exposure.

Reference	Technology	Environment	Phantom	Precoding and number of UEs	Exposure metrics	Power normalization	Focus
[28]	D-MIMO mMIMO	indoor industrial	heterogeneous head and neck	MRT (1 UE)	S_{inc} SAR_{10g}	radiated power incident power	S_{inc} around head phantom SAR_{10g} in head phantom
[29]	D-MIMO mMIMO	indoor industrial	heterogeneous head	MRT (1 UE) CZF (2 and 3 UEs)	E -field SAR_{10g}	output power	E -field around head phantom SAR_{10g} in head phantom
This work	D-MIMO mMIMO	indoor industrial	homogeneous full-body	EGT (1 UE) CZF (2 and 4 UEs)	S_{inc} SAR_{10g} SAR_{WB}	configured power radiated power received power	S_{inc} SAR in body phantom

malization conditions, and number of reflections. Therefore, increasing further the number of rays-geometry interactions is not expected to have significant impact on the comparative study for different deployments. Moreover, the exposure levels were found to be hundreds or thousands of times below the limit values. While the determined exposure levels might change slightly by adjusting the simulation parameters, the main conclusions will not change.

The study can be further extended by using different types of BS and UE antennas, more DRU or mMIMO antenna positions, more UE and phantom positions, denser field strength sampling, etc. In addition, the study is performed only at 3.5 GHz.

A comparison between this paper and relevant works in the literature is given in Table VII. Particularly, array antennas were used to model individual D-MIMO DRUs in this paper, and the effects of the number of D-MIMO DRUs on the EMF exposure levels were investigated. Also, a full-body homogeneous phantom was used to evaluate both local and whole-body SAR. In [28], [29] heterogeneous phantoms with the human head and neck and human head, respectively, have been used. It should be mentioned that a heterogeneous phantom can also be used in the proposed workflow, particularly in the time-domain solver. More power normalization conditions were considered in this paper. The DL environmental exposure in terms of S_{inc} was evaluated in this paper, while only the region around the user's head has been considered for user's exposure in [28], [29]. Also, local- and whole-body SAR for DL exposure was evaluated for the 1-m separation distance between the UE and the phantom, while the local-SAR in [28], [29] was evaluated for the UE antenna located within a few cm from the head phantom. In the used asymptotic solver, the UE antenna was represented as the far-field source, requiring that the phantom should be placed outside the far-field region of the dipole. For shorter distances, the UE antenna may need to be represented using a near-field source to account for the near-field interaction between the UE antenna and the phantom. This would further increase the computational burden. Future works are needed for hybrid simulations using the near-field sources for similar deployment scenarios.

In general, the conclusions from [28], [29] and this paper are similar that the simulated exposure levels are far below the limits. For example, the 95th percentile in [28] has been found to be below 5% and 1% of the ICNIRP limits for S_{inc} and SAR_{10g} , respectively, for an output power of 320 W. The corresponding value for SAR_{10g} in [29] has found to be below 0.1% for an output power of 1 W. More results can be found

in the corresponding papers.

Future extensions of the work can be on several topics. For example, it is of interest to assess the EMF exposure with more advanced precoding schemes, and precoding schemes associated with a DRU selection method, using only some of the DRUs for DL transmission [3].

Currently, the investigative research on D-MIMO is ongoing, for example, in the Hexa-X-II project [9]. It is difficult to predict today how future D-MIMO networks will be designed. When the technical specifications are standardized, the scenarios and assumptions in this study may need to be refined and confirmed.

VI. CONCLUSION

A hybrid simulation scheme for performing EMF exposure studies for D-MIMO deployments has been developed. The same scheme has also been applied to a mMIMO deployment for comparison purposes under the same conditions. The EMF exposure, including the metrics of incident power density, 10g-SAR, and WBSAR, have been assessed using two antenna precoding schemes including EGT and CZF, and considering three different power normalization conditions. The study has been performed in a realistic industrial indoor environment at 3.5 GHz. The impact of different numbers of DRUs and UEs on EMF exposure levels has been studied.

For all selected D-MIMO and mMIMO configurations and power conditions, the assessed EMF levels are far below the limits. For the investigated D-MIMO scenario, the maximum 95th percentiles of 10-g SAR and WBSAR have been found below 0.08% and 0.06% of the respective limits for general public, and the maximum 99th percentile of the incident power density has been found below 0.06% of the ICNIRP limits for general public. These levels are also lower than the respective 95th and 99th percentiles of EMF exposure levels for the investigated mMIMO deployment scenario under the same power conditions. For the median value, no trend that one of the deployments constantly leads to a higher EMF exposure is observed, i.e., mMIMO can lead to lower, similar, or higher exposure compared to D-MIMO. It has been seen that the precoding scheme has impact on the exposure levels, and the difference between the precoding schemes, in terms of EMF exposure, also depends on the imposed power normalization condition. The results have demonstrated that a smaller number of DRUs (6 DRUs) deployed in the environment leads to higher 95th and 99th percentiles than a larger number of DRUs (24 DRUs). With more simultaneously served UEs in the network, the lower 95th and 99th percentiles

of EMF exposure levels have been found for both mMIMO and D-MIMO. Since 6G studies are in an early phase, it is expected that the proposed method and findings will be of great interest in EMF exposure research for 6G D-MIMO deployment scenarios.

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